

CLINICAL ANATOMY OF THE HAND

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Annotation. The article provides data on the clinical anatomy of the hand, which is usually not found in well-known domestic and foreign manuals. This information is very important for understanding the specifics of the new branch of surgery, which emerged from traumatology and became a separate specialty - hand surgery.

Key words: mythological anatomy of the hand, blood supply to the hand.

The hand is a person's mediator in contact with the outside world. The hand is an organ of labor in all the variety of professions. She carries out the will of man in mechanical acts and in mental experiences. The hand is an organ of touch; The blind have the organ of vision, and the dumb have the organ of speech. The loss of a hand is tragic. An unrivaled instrument is dying. But at the same time, something more is lost: the most creative parts of the brain are brought to a dead end. After all, the territory of the projection of the hand in the anterior and posterior central convolutions of the cerebral cortex has almost the same extent as the rest of the body. Time, labor and past illnesses leave their mark on the hand. Moreover, there are no wrinkles on the face yet, and the hand is already losing the expressiveness of the pose, the mobility of the joints, and the shine of the nails. With age, the fingers become knotty, the skin on the back of the hand becomes covered with many folds, and brown spots of pigment appear on it. The skin becomes thinner and loses elasticity; an expanded venous network emerges through it. Atrophy of the subcutaneous fatty tissue, muscles of the eminence of the thumb and little finger leads to flattening of the palmar cup. By its appearance, the hand "speaks" about the profession; it can signal the presence of common diseases and bad habits in a person.

When examining the hand, in addition to local changes, you can obtain information about the condition of the entire body. "Marbled" skin can indirectly indicate chronic nephritis, a pronounced pattern of veins in the back of the hand - stasis in the lungs, "drum" fingers - chronic oxygen starvation of the body, periarticular deposits - gout. Flattened nail plates in the shape of a watch glass are observed in diseases of the lungs (bronchiectasis, emphysema), but are never observed in congenital heart defects.

The fatty tissue of the palm is very specific in its structure and is found in humans only in two areas: on the vola manus and planta pedis. The subcutaneous tissue in the palm area is cellular; contains a dense network of vertical and spiral elastic fibers that firmly fix the skin to the palmar aponeurosis. This structure provides a stable and reliable clamping grip. The subcutaneous tissue of the palm is divided by fascial spurs from the edges of the palmar aponeurosis to the skin into three sections, corresponding to the central recess of the palm and the eminences of the thumb (thenar) and little finger (hypothenar). In the thenar region , the thickness of the fiber increases from the outside to the inside and penetrates under the superficial spur of the palmar aponeurosis, into the first interdigital space. In the area of the central recess of the palm, thin fascial plates run from the skin to the palmar aponeurosis, forming within this recess a series of channels filled with adipose tissue. The subcutaneous

tissue of the hypothenar is quite thick (up to 6–8 mm); it is located in two layers across the palmaris brevis muscle: a denser superficial one and a looser deep one.

On the palmar surface of the hand, three areas are distinguished: the area of the eminence of the thumb (thenar), the area of the eminence of the little finger (hypothenar) and the palm itself (the central part of the palm). In the central part of the palm are the tendons of the superficial and deep flexor muscles of the fingers, the vessels of the superficial and deep palmar arches and the median nerve. The skin pattern of the palm itself is represented by three constant transverse folds: the distal palmar fold (“head line”), the middle palmar fold (“heart line”), the proximal palmar fold (“life line”) and the main (axial) longitudinal direction. The transverse folds of the palm and the palmar surface of the fingers are slightly mobile areas of the skin; there is no subcutaneous fatty tissue, and the skin itself is firmly fixed directly to the underlying fascia.

The distal transverse line of the palm (distal palmar fold) or “head line” in palmists is a skin fold that is located above the three medial (III–V) metacarpophalangeal joints. It is sometimes called the “ulnar line” because it always extends to the medial edge of the palm.

The proximal transverse line of the palm is located 1 cm proximal to the previous line (“heart line” among palmists) on the outer side passes over the metacarpophalangeal joint of the index finger and usually reaches the lateral edge of the palm. In some cases, this line is called the “radial line”.

The palmar surface of the fingers is delimited from the palm by the finger-palmar fold. The four three-phalanx fingers are separated from each other by the second, third and fourth interdigital spaces (they are deeper on the back side).

Immediately below the interdigital folds, on the palm in the spaces between the fingers, there are three oval-shaped elevations - fatty “pads”. They correspond to the area of the three commissural openings of the palmar aponeurosis.

The proximal interphalangeal fold is double, separating the proximal phalanx from the middle one (on fingers II–V) and the proximal phalanx from the distal one on the thumb.

The thumb is separated from the outer edge of the hand by a wide and deep interdigital space. Between it and the eminence of the thumb there are two finger-palm folds. They are located slightly distal to the level of the interphalangeal joint of the thumb.

The transverse skin folds of the palm and the folds of the dorsum of the hand end in the so-called “neutral lines” (Fig. 6). These are lines that are not subject to tensile forces when the hand is clenched into a fist and (or) the fingers are straightened. In other words, when the skin on the palm or dorsum of the hand moves, contracts, or stretches, the skin in the area of the “neutral lines” behaves relatively neutrally. When incisions are made along neutral lines or transverse folds of the palm, postoperative scars are usually normotrophic .

The skin of the palmar surface of the hand is also characterized by fine wrinkles caused by the presence of rugae and sulci cutis . The skin pattern thus formed is so specific that it serves to identify the individual. The finest papillary lines or skin ridges are thickenings of the epidermal layer of the skin. Underneath them lie the dermal papillae (the papillary layer of the dermis) with their corresponding vascular networks located in the horizontal and vertical directions. The unique skin pattern in different individuals is due to individual the architectonics of the dermal papillae and, accordingly, the intradermal vascular bed.

Since time immemorial, different peoples have formed a lot of myths about the brush. Our ancestors cannot be denied observation skills.

Much new and interesting information in the anatomy of the hand can be found by studying these myths. In ancient rock paintings, the left hand most often appears, because the right hand was most likely used for painting. In most mythological representations, the left hand embodied the negative principle, impurity. Therefore, it was often used for blowing the nose and washing the intimate organs. The right hand could become “defiled” by the left one. In left-handed people, the corresponding hand is larger, they have better developed (pronounced) veins on the back of the left hand and a better developed nail on the little finger. “Right-handedness” has been characteristic of most people since prehistoric times (90%), only 10% of people are “left-handed.” “Left-handedness” appears from about 6 months or even later, when the child begins to sit up. By the age of one and a half years, it becomes completely clear which hand is “leading” and which is “auxiliary”. There are many theories of “right-handedness.” According to the “anatomical theory”, right-handedness depends on the asymmetry of the organs: the heavier liver is located on the right, and the heart on the left. The unequal blood supply to the upper extremities also plays a role. There is a point of view that initially the number of right-handers and left-handers was almost the same. At the dawn of the emergence of Homo sapiens, the functional and anatomical asymmetry of the cerebral hemispheres was manifested in the fact that left-handers, who had less rational thinking, were more sensitive (maybe less careful) to substances (poisons) affecting brain activity. Left-handers died quickly, right-handers escaped with only a slight illness. And they produced a stable of right-handed offspring. According to modern observations of clinicians, among left-handers, patients with temporal lobe epilepsy, with “cleft lip”, and “allergy sufferers” are more often observed. But among left-handers there are more mathematicians. They are more inclined and successful in music and drawing than others. Retraining a child to be left-handed is fraught with the appearance of a large number of neurological abnormalities, including stuttering, bedwetting, etc.

References:

1. Volkov M.V. Modern methods of treating hand injuries // Let's make it up . method of treating injuries and diseases of the hand. - M., 1975. — P. 3–10.
2. Boychev B., Bozhkov Vl., Mateev Iv . and others. Surgery of the hand and fingers. — Sofia: “Medicine and physical education.” - 1971. — 279 p.
3. Zolotko Yu. L. Atlas of topographic human anatomy. - M.: “Medicine”, 1976. - Part III. — 296 p.
4. Kirpatovsky I. D., Smirnova E. D. Clinical anatomy: In 2 books. Book 2: Upper and lower limbs. - M.:
5. Medical Information Agency, 2003. - 316 p.
6. Kosh R. Hand surgery. - Budapest: Publishing House of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, 1966. - 511 p.
7. Usoltseva E. V., Mashkara K. I. Surgery of diseases and injuries of the hand. - M.: "Medicine", 1978. - 336 p.

8. Etingen L. E. Mythological anatomy. - M.: "Institute of General Humanitarian Research", 2006. - 528 p.
9. Biemer E., Duspiva W. Reconstructive microvascular surgery. - Berlin; Heidelberg; NY: Springer- Verlag, 1982. - 151 r.
10. Conway H. and R. B. Stark Arterial vascularization of the soft tissues of the hand // J. Bone Joint Surg. (Am). - 1954. - Vol . 36-A, No. 6. - P. 1238–1240.
11. Elsner T., Schramm U. and Schrader M. Analysis of the vascular anatomy of the palm and its clinical relevance in Morbus Dupuytren // Ann. Anat . - 2001. - Vol . 183(4). — P. 379–382.
12. Schmidt H.-M., Lanz U. Surgical anatomy. — Stuttgart; NY: Thieme , 2004. - 259 rub .
13. Southwood WFW The thickness of the skin // Plast.Reconstr . Surg. - 1955. - Vol. 15. - P. 423–429.

